

THE EFFECT OF INTERCULTURAL RELATIONSHIPS IN LANGUAGE
LEARNING

Ergashev Asror Jasur o'g'li

Termiz State University

Faculty of Foreign Philology

4th year student of philology and language teaching

Annatation : This article discusses the role of intercultural communication and communication in language learning. And at the same time, an attempt was made to reveal the essence of the topic.

Key words : communication skills , multicultural , cross-cultural communication.

The fact that the relations of mutual cooperation between the peoples of the world in various fields are expanding more and more requires such new areas and directions of linguistics. Because each nation and people have their own, unique standards of communication, without knowing them people of different countries cannot communicate with each other. That's why it is necessary to learn foreign languages or the communication behavior of people living in different regions who speak the same language.

Intercultural communication is included in every foreign language lesson. In it, cultures can be compared. In this process, it becomes clear that the study of dialect is aimed at studying the speech habits of social groups that differ from other members of society in terms of their language, but for most sociolinguists, their field is closely related to dialectology. It is observed that they imagine. At this point, it should be mentioned that in terms of its main interest, dialectology differs sharply from modern sociolinguistics.

Dialectology and sociolinguistics differ in one more place - in choosing the initial unit of the object of analysis. Dialectology interprets languages and dialects as integrated systems. In fact, there should be clearly visible dividing lines between these systems: isoglosses, that is, the lines connecting settlements with the same language characteristics on the linguistic map, clearly depend on this interpretation. At a time when the times are rapidly developing, the need to establish cooperative relations with foreign citizens in economic, cultural, scientific and educational areas is increasing. This, in turn, leads to an increase in the demand for learning a foreign language on an international scale, to the fact that communities are becoming multilingual and multicultural day by day, and to the formation of intercultural communication skills. Students studying in any field of education will not face

obstacles and misunderstandings when communicating only if they have information about the culture and customs of the people of the language they are studying. Importantly, before engaging with non-native speakers, it is important to fully understand the cultural differences that exist in order to avoid relationship breakdowns that result from cross-cultural communication gaps. We must always be aware that the norms, beliefs, practices and language of any group are dynamic rather than static. From a linguistic point of view, culture plays an important role in teaching and learning a foreign language. It is known that language is used as the main tool of culture. In order to understand what intercultural communication is in learning and teaching foreign languages, it is first necessary to consider the pure concept of culture. It also requires knowledge about the meaning of language as the main factor of intercultural communication in learning and teaching foreign languages. Often students are taught the rules of the language but fail to communicate adequately because they do not know enough about the target culture. In view of this issue, it is very important that students have knowledge about the culture of the language being studied from the beginning. The reform of the educational system should take into account the development of international relations, and at the same time, we should form students' knowledge and skills about the language norms of the country they are studying, their customs and traditions. English, which has the status of an international language in the world community, is one of the high-level languages used in the intellectual, economic, commercial and cultural aspects of the world's life. Learning this language is very important in establishing intercultural relations, increasing the potential of international tourism, conveying information through mass media, and finally in developing the education system. Teachers and students who want to communicate effectively in educational settings, regionally and globally, should, first of all, sufficiently learn the language and culture of the interlocutor. Intercultural communication skills can be defined as the learner's ability to perceive, analyze, and relate different cultures to their native language and nationality. No matter how much the modern man lives in a globalized world, I believe that people now need to know their family, region, nation, country, or cultural information messages first. A person cannot understand the culture of another nation without being constantly aware of his cultural roots.

REFERENCES :

1. Mirziyoev Sh.M. Buyuk kelajagimizni mard va olijanob xalqimiz bilan birga quramiz. -Toshkent: "O'zbekifon" NMIU, 2017. - 488b.
2. Byram M.Cultural studies in foreign language education. - Clevedon: Multicultural atters Ltd., 1989. - 165p.
3. Елизарова Г.В., Герсета А.И. Кура/гура и обучение иностранным языкам /- СПб., Изд-во РГПУ им. 2004. - 291 с.
4. Малкова, Е.В. Формирование межкультурной компетенции в процессе работы над текстами для чтения немецкий язык в неязыковом вузе, факультет с расширенной сеткой часов: дис. ... кандлед^ук: 3.00.02 / Малкова Елеш Валеревна.- М., 2000.-263 с.